

PHYSICAL CHEMISTRY OF RESIN SOLUTIONS. PART II. NATURE OF RESIN SOLUTIONS IN ORGANIC SOLVENTS.

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Solutions of natural resins, particularly shellac in organic solvents like alcohol, acetone, etc. have been found to be non-colloidal since they rapidly dialyse out, pass through ultrafilters easily, are devoid of Tyndall effect and have considerable osmotic properties. The soft resin and pure resin of shellac are present in shellac as mechanical mixture since they diffuse in solution independently of each other. Pure resin of shellac has been found to be homogeneous in molecular mass as it could not be separated into fractions with different melting points and acid values, by dialysis

Alcoholic solutions of natural resins, perhaps due to their association with varnishes are often assumed to be colloidal and this idea is freely mentioned in literature without any convincing experimental support. Thus, Zsigmondy ("Chemistry of Colloids," Eng. Trans. p. 32) places resins in the class of colloids like rubber, etc. which are soluble in an organic medium. This is particularly true of shellac solutions whose colloidal nature is assumed by a number of workers including Gardner and collaborators (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1929, 21, 227; *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1929, 1, 207) and Verman (Technical Paper No. 11 of London Shellac Research Bureau, pp. 4, 11) without any definite experimental evidence. Even Tschirch and Stock ("Die Harze", 1932, Band I, p. 147) are inclined to believe natural resins and their solutions as colloids and they quote the work of one of their students, Siedels, who attempts to prove the colloidal nature of resin solutions in alcohol by direct dialysis in parchment. Another observation relevant to the subject is that of Wo. Ostwald (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1920-21, 16, General Discussion, p. 89), who finds that natural resins and all other substances which spontaneously dissolve in alcohol have a perceptible rate of diffusion through collodion membranes which points to the fact that at least a part of the resin is present in true solution.

Since substances like dyes, soaps etc. which are colloidal in aqueous medium have been found out to be molecularly disperse in alcoholic solutions, it is quite probable that such solutions of natural resins may also be molecularly disperse. And the fact that most natural resins have molecular weights generally less than 2000, but usually between 300 and 700, debars them from being molecular colloids, and warrants the possibility that alcoholic solutions of the resins may be true solutions and not colloidal.

The purpose of the present paper is to investigate the nature of resin solutions in organic solvents with special reference to shellac. The problem has been investigated having regard to the following characteristic properties of colloids *viz.*, dialysis, ultrafiltration, Tyndall effect and osmotic properties.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Dialysis.

Investigation in alcoholic solution is rendered difficult for want of a suitable semipermeable membrane in alcoholic solution. Parchment paper is useless as being very slow in action and not perfectly wetted by alcohol, and membranes of collodion and cellophane were tried as Wo. Ostwald (*loc. cit.*) previously used them with some success in alcoholic solution. Best results were, however, obtained by using alcohol-insoluble ultrafiltration membranes (commercially called ultra-cella filters) manufactured by de Haen works of Germany. The membrane was stretched across the bottom of a circular dialyser and tightly fixed there with rubber washers and suitable nuts. Dialysis was carried out with 20 c.c. of 20% dewaxed shellac solution in redistilled industrial spirit under a tightly fitting bell jar to prevent evaporation of alcohol. The results with different membranes are given below.

(a) *Collodion Membrane.*—Both the resins present in shellac dialyse with great rapidity through such membranes and there is considerable osmosis. With 500 c.c. of alcohol as outside liquid, more than 50% of the total resin diffuse out in about 6 hours and the outside and inside concentrations equalise in about 24 hours. But the experiment is very difficult to carry out for any length of time, as the membranes swell and become soft in contact with alcohol, and in a few hours usually burst either due to osmotic rise or to slight mechanical shock.

(b) *Ultrafiltration Membrane.*—With ultrafilters of the grade 'ultra-cella' (finest) which is capable of retaining not only the finest gold sol but even albumins, shellac solutions in organic solvents diffuse with extreme ease. The resin may be detected in the dialysate in less than half an hour. Through a 9 cm. diameter membrane using 500 c.c. of alcohol outside and changing it once in three days, more than 50% diffuse out in the first three days and practically the whole quantity of shellac diffuses out during 4 to 5 changes. That nothing colloidal is left inside after this period is shown by completely ultrafiltering the residual inside liquid through the same membrane.

(c) *Cellophane Membrane*.—With cellophane both the resins diffuse out comparatively slowly and make their presence detectable in the dialysate only after three to six hours. The slow rate is further shown by the fact that only about 20% pass through in one week.

Composition of Dialysate.

The proportion of soft resin and pure resin present in the dialysate was determined analytically and shows the following figures for the very permeable collodion membrane for the first six hours, after which the membrane burst for reasons already mentioned (outside liquid—200 c.c. alcohol).

TABLE I.

Composition of dialysate during various stages of dialysis.

Collodion membrane.	Percentage of soft resin (ether soluble).	Percentage of hard resin.
Original shellac	29.6	70.4
0-2 hours' dialysate	52.3	47.7
2-4 hours' dialysate	50.4	49.6
4-6 hours' dialysate	47.3	52.7
Ultra-cella' membrane.		
Original shellac	29.6	70.4
Dialysate after 40 hours	38.7	61.3
Residue after 40 hours	18.3	81.7

The above table shows that the proportion of soft resin and hard resin continually changes in the dialysate as well as in the residual solutions. This conclusively shows that the constituents of shellac are not chemically combined but are co-existent in the solution as a mixture in approximately molecular proportion and diffuse independently, in contradiction to the idea of some previous workers (Verman and Bhattacharya, London Shellac Research Bureau Technical Paper No. 1).

Ultrafiltration.

A Zsigmondy type 9 cm. ultrafilter, modified as described below was used with 'ultracella' membranes of 'fine' and 'finest' variety. The

filter was closed with a tight fitting rubber stopper which was pressed down and kept in place by a circular brass sheet from above. The brass sheet in its turn was pressed down to the body of the filter with suitable nuts and connecting rods. The rubber cork was fitted with two glass tubes, one for connecting to a pressure gauge, while the other was connected to a pressure tubing fitted with an ordinary cycle-valve, through which air was pumped in to apply pressure. This arrangement is not only a convenient modification of the apparatus but is essentially necessary for use with volatile organic solvents. Otherwise, if suction is applied from below high vacuum is not created due to the high saturation pressure of the solvent; and secondly, the solvent quickly evaporates off the bottom surface of the membrane depositing a solid film of resin on it, which hinders its further permeability. That the membranes have not ruptured during experiment was always tested with Zsigmondy's gold sol after washing the membrane with the organic solvent used and then with water. Pressure of about 25 lbs. per square inch was used. The results obtained are summarised below.

(a) Solutions of shellac in alcohol upto concentrations of 20% were tried and were found to pass unchanged rapidly through the finest membranes. As the concentration of shellac increases, the filtration becomes less rapid due evidently to increased viscosity. The solutions obtained on addition of water to the above solution also ultrafilters completely right up to the precipitation point of shellac, if the ultrafiltration is carried out immediately. On standing fine particles of shellac separate out from the solution and remain suspended as a coarse colloid.

(b) 5% Alcoholic solutions of rosin, mastic, accroides and pontianac were tested and were found to pass completely and very rapidly through the finest ultrafilter. It is really remarkable that the pontianac solutions behave in this way, for its alcoholic solution become turbid on dilution with more alcohol, which is generally believed to be due to the presence of colloidal particles. But the true explanation is a different one as has been proved by the author in a previous publication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 308).

(c) Solutions of shellac (5% and 10% by weight) in aqueous acetone (10% water) were tested and were found to pass completely through the ultrafilter quite easily. Similar solution of about 20% strength also passes through the membrane but the rate is extremely slow (about 10 c.c. in 24 hours). The identity of the filtrate and the residual liquid on the filter was established by a determination of their density and refractive index.

Tyndall Effect.

The technique used was a very simple one and followed very closely to that recommended by Hatchek ('Practical Colloid Chemistry'). Carbon arc lamp was used as the light source with suitable condensing system of lenses (an epidiascope was used), and filters to cut off heat rays. The electric arc worked on a current of about 4 amperes with a drop of 110 volts between its terminals. The solution to be tested was contained in a glass cell made of highly transparent plane glass. This arrangement was tested before use with typical colloids, *e.g.* Zsigmondy's gold sol, mastic sol, etc.

All the resin solutions used in the ultrafiltration experiments were tested. They were all optically void just like ordinary alcohol except the solutions which contained a large percentage of water and were close to the precipitation point. This absence of Tyndall effect is an agreement with the observations of previous workers (Bender in Alexander's "Colloid Chemistry," Vol. IV), who invariably failed to disclose the existence of colloidal particles in resin solutions by ultramicroscopic examination.

Osmotic Properties.

The osmotic properties of resin solutions in so far as freezing point depressions and boiling point elevations are concerned have been studied by many different workers to gain an idea of the molecular weights of the resins. Thus the boiling point elevation of abietic acid (the main constituent of resin) solutions in acetone has been very carefully determined recently by Bender (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1812) who has found a mean molecular weight of 378 as against the theoretical value of 302. From Tschrich and Stocks' book, it appears that a closer agreement than this is usual with most of the components of natural resins. The molecular weight of shellac in alcohol has been determined in this laboratory with the Cottrell's apparatus and also elsewhere, and has been found to have an average value of 1000.

Freezing point depressions of shellac solutions in dioxane and glacial acetic acid have been studied (Palit and Bhattacharya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 258) and have always yielded values of 1000 for shellac, about 600 for soft resin (ether soluble) and 1800-2000 for pure resin (ether-insoluble). Even the fossilized copals have been found to yield an average molecular weight of 500 by cryoscopic measurements by different workers. This shows that the resin molecules are hardly associated in solution in organic solvents to form large micelles of colloidal dimension.

DISCUSSION.

The position with regard to the nature of natural resin solutions has hitherto not been very clear. No systematic colloidal investigation has yet been undertaken with this end in view, but a number of molecular weight determinations by cryoscopic methods has been made in connection with the study of the individual components isolated from natural resins. In most cases, an approximate agreement with the values arrived at from chemical evidence is obtained, which shows that at least in dilute solutions these resin components form true solutions. But coming to the question of the solutions of natural resins themselves, they are almost universally supposed to be colloidal. Such an assumption rests on some indirect evidences. All resin solutions under suitable conditions of temperature and concentration are capable of forming gels which are commonly believed to be di-phasic and since solutions of resins are nothing but these gels simply with a greater proportion of solvent, a colloid structure for them is assumed as a natural corollary. Houwink's isogel concept for resins ("Natur- und Kunst-harze," 1934; cf. "British Plastic Year Book" 1935, p. 51) in the solid state has also materially contributed to strengthen this widespread belief for resin solutions.

The evidences presented herein, show that the assumption of colloidal nature is here totally unjustified. The idea of a reversible micellar aggregation of a part of the resin in solution, though conceivable, is not supported by osmotic evidences, as the observed molecular weights are of an order too low for micelle formation. Rapid dialysis may, however, well be explained by the micellar theory as being due to the dissociation of micelles to the simplest units which pass through the membrane and recombine on other side, but such micelles must be extremely few in number as osmotic results show. Though a strong Tyndall effect is a positive proof of the presence of colloids, its absence, as is well known, may not be a sure indication of true solution, since the Tyndall effect depends not only on the particle size but also on the difference in refractive indices between the dispersed phase and the medium. The ultrafiltration experiment is, however, very definite in its indication and is irreconcilable with a micellar theory. For substances like soap, where micellar aggregation is definitely established, it is known from the work of McBain and Jenkins (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922 121, 2325), that only a very small portion passes through the ultrafilters as against the resin solutions investigated here where the whole solution passes through unchanged in composition in a few minutes. The effectiveness of these membranes, for organic solvents

has already been established by Kumichael (*Koll.-chem. Beih.*, 1928, 28, 151), who using a cella ultrafilter obtained an ultrafiltrate of practically pure acetone from its nitrocellulose solutions. In this connection an ultrafiltration experiment quoted by Traxlar (*Chem. Rev.*, 1936, 19, 125) is interesting. On ultrafiltering petroleum, both soft and hard asphalts dissolved in petroleum, were quantitatively retained on the ultrafilter, whereas the associated resin passes through the filter in petroleum solution. An additional proof of the non-existence of micelles or loosely bound aggregates in natural resin solutions is furnished by Houwink ("Physikalische Eigenschaften und Feinbau von Natur-und Kunstharzen," 1934, p. 206) who from viscometric investigations of such solutions arrived at the same conclusion. It seems, therefore, highly probable that resin solutions are non-colloidal in spite of their great gel-forming capacities. Of course, gel-forming tendency is not necessarily associated with a colloidal structure as proved in the case of alcoholic solutions of soaps (*vide*, Lederer, "Kolloid Chemie der Seifen," 1932, pp. 78, 229) or linseed oil, pure or moderately oxidised, which according to Freundlich (*J. Oil & Colour Chem. Assoc.*, 1935, 18, 74) is non-colloidal since its benzene solution easily passes through the ultrafilter.

For shellac it has sometimes been postulated (Bhattacharya and Gidvani, London Shellac Research Bureau, Technical Paper No. 16) that it is composed of all sorts of polymers ranging from 300 to 3,000 in molecular weight. Our experiences have always been to the contrary so far as diffusion experiments are concerned. In one of our experiments pure resin solution in alcohol was dialysed in the finest ultrafilter membrane. The dialysates at different stages of dialysis and also the residue were compared with one another and were found to be identical in acid values and melting points within the limits of experimental error. If pure resin were composed of molecules differing widely in molecular weights, we could reasonably expect to effect some segregation of heavy and light molecules by dialysis with consequent difference in melting points and acid values of these fractions.

The absence of all typical and fundamental colloidal properties in resin solutions *e.g.*, low rate of diffusion, negligible lowering of vapour pressure, Tyndall effect and retention on ultrafilters, makes it imperative to explain the so-called colloidal properties of resin solutions *e.g.*, high viscosity, tendency towards gel formation, characteristic tackiness, etc., on solvation basis. There is no doubt that solvation is an essential phenomenon in such solutions but the inadequate nature of our knowledge of solvation stands in our way to any fruitful discussion on the point. It seems that Stewart's conception

(*Chem. Rev.*, 1929, 6, 483; *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1937, 33, 239) of cybotactic groups' or evanescent swarms may be nearer to truth for such solution, a view advocated by Bender (*loc. cit.*) who brings out some experimental evidence in its support.

The important question now arises whether resin solutions should be regarded as systems in thermodynamic equilibrium or not. In other words, we are to answer the question, given the temperature and concentration of the system, are all other properties definite and invariable for such a system? We must admit that at the present state of our knowledge an unequivocal answer is not available. For intrinsic colloids like high-molecular-weight synthetic resins, it is the general experience that the properties of the resin solutions depend to some extent on the past history of the same but in not such a remarkable manner as the aqueous solutions of gelatin, albumen, etc. This is clearly brought out by the cryoscopic measurements of Bender (*loc. cit.*) on solutions of rosin and some phenolic resins where he finds a considerable difference in the boiling point elevations of similar solutions prepared in slightly different manner. The same worker finds that the viscosity of resin solutions changes slowly with time. It appears, therefore, that the properties of such solutions are not defined completely by two parameters but have some degree of latitude within short limits, which in its turn depends on the structural complexity of the resin and its affinity for the solvent. Recently, however, Papkov and co-workers (*Acta Physicochem.*, 1938, 3, 647) have found out that in the dissolved state of highly polymerised substance, molecular dispersions are obtained, and the phase rule is completely applicable to the system, highly polymerised substance-solvent.

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